

Retrospective Analysis of Cesarean Section Performed in Second Stage and its Maternal Outcome**Lithingo Lotha¹, Asha Borah², Johnson Brahma³, Shamim Ahmed⁴**¹Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam, India.²Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam, India.³Postgraduate Trainee, Department of Obstetrics and gynecology, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam, India.⁴Postgraduate Trainee, Department of Obstetrics and gynecology, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam, India.

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Abstract:**Background:** Second stage caesarean section are associated with more complications than first stage due to fully dilated cervix and deeply engaged head.**Aims and Objectives:** To study the intraoperative as well as postoperative complications associated with caesarean section performed in the second stage of labor.**Methods:** Data was collected from the hospital records of Assam Medical College. It included all the term pregnancies i.e. >37 weeks from April 2023 to March 2024.**Results:** Out of total 11781 deliveries 5658 was caesarean section, out of which 1150 was performed in the second stage. The most common cause was arrest of descent (44%) followed by fetal distress (19.6%), occipito posterior position (14.1%). The most common complications were blood transfusion (21%) followed by uterine incision extension (15.0%). The most common postoperative complications were prolonged catheterization (5.6%), abdominal distension (3%), febrile illness (2.1%).**Conclusion:** Complications are common in second stage caesarean section and trained obstetricians should perform it to minimize the complication.**Keywords:** Cesarean Section, Second Stage, Maternal Outcomes.

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Introduction

The second stage of labor is the interval from complete dilation of cervix until the fetus is delivered. [1] On average, this stage lasts 50 minutes for first-time mothers (nullipara) and 20 minutes for women who have given birth before (multipara). A prolonged second stage is identified when it exceeds 2 hours in nullipara and 1 hour in multipara. Arrest of descent is diagnosed when there is no progress in the baby's position for at least 2 hours. [2] One typical surgery performed in obstetrics is the Cesarean section. Its rate has been increasing since then due its increase in popularity and the use of good anesthesia and improved antibiotics, decrease in the rate of instrumental deliveries and cesarean on maternal request. [3] Cesarean section is associated with more complications than vaginal deliveries. The rate of complications depends on the stage at which the c-section is performed.

Even though the safety of Cesarean section has improved over time, there are still a few risks and complications associated with the process that can result

in morbidity and mortality of the mother as well as the fetus.

At the second stage, the commonly performed interventions are instrumental delivery and cesarean section. Globally, 10-20% of deliveries in second stage necessitate some type of intervention, often involving a cesarean section. Instrumental vaginal deliveries, including forceps and vacuum extraction, make up 7-11% of births. [4] At the second stage the mother has a fully dilated cervix and deeply engaged head which poses a risk to both mother and fetus [3]. During the second stage of labor, the lower uterine segment typically stretches or thins out and is "taken up," making it susceptible to lacerations and tears. [5] Therefore, the uterine incision should be made slightly higher than it would be for an antepartum or first stage cesarean section: Some of the common complications in cesarean section performed in second stage are- uterine incision extension, hemorrhage, bladder injury, bowel injury etc. [1]

RCOG has identified that maximum of the

complications was seen when the caesarean section was performed by a junior staff. [6] Second stage caesarean section is not only associated with increased maternal mortality but also increased neonatal morbidity. In this study we are focused on maternal morbidity only.

Aims and Objectives

To study the intraoperative as well as postoperative complications associated with cesarean section performed in the second stage.

To know the rate of cesarean section in Assam Medical College and Hospital.

Materials and Methods

Study Type: Hospital based retrospective observational study was conducted in Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh Assam from April 2023 to March 2024, on all the pregnant patients visiting the OPD and the emergency departments whose period of gestation was more than 37 weeks. The study included only those patients who were in

the second stage of labor and were taken for emergency LSCS.

Data Collection: Records were collected from the hospital records of the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Assam Medical College.

The following data were collected:

1. Total number of deliveries both vaginal and cesarean.
2. Date and time of cesarean
3. Maternal age, parity, gestational weeks
4. Indication for cesarean
5. Intraoperative and postoperative complications.

Results

During the study period a total of 11781 deliveries occurred, 6123 was vaginal delivery (51.97%) and 5658 cesarean section (48.02%). Out of the total cesarean section conducted, 1150 was performed in second stage (20.3%).

Table 1: Rate and mode of delivery from April 2023 to March 2024

Mode of delivery	Vaginal deliveries	Cesarean section
Numbers	6123 (51.97%)	5658 (48.02%)

In the present study the rate of vaginal delivery is 51.97% and cesarean section rate is 48.02% in Assam Medical College and Hospital.

Baseline Characteristics of Women Undergoing Cesarean Sections

Table 2: According to Age

Age Group	Number	Percentage
<25	489	42.5
25-30	502	43.7
30-35	111	9.7
>35	47	4.1

In the present study the maximum number of patients belong to the age group of 25-30. (43.7)

Table 3: According to Gravidity

Gravida	Number	Percentage
Primi	830	72.2
Multi	320	27.8

In the present study the maximum number of patients were primigravida (72.2%).

Figure 1: Pie diagram depicting gravidity

Table 4: Indications for Cesarean Section

Indications	Number	Percentage
Arrest of descent	506	44.0
fetal distress	225	19.6
Occipito posterior position	162	14.1
Deep transverse arrest	104	9.1
obstructed labour	115	10.0
Failed instrumental delivery	34	3.0
2nd twin non vertex	2	0.2

In the present study the most common indication was arrest of descent (44.0%) followed by fetal distress (19.6%) then occipito posterior position (14.1%).

Figure 2: Bar diagram depicting Indications of Cesarean Section

Complications

Table 5: Intraoperative Complications

Complications	Number	Percentage
Atonic PPH	108	9.4
Uterine extension	172	15.0
Angle hematoma	49	4.3
Blood transfusion	241	21.0
Vaginal injury	11	1.0
Bladder injury	9	0.8
Hematuria	70	6.1

In the present study the most common intraoperative complications seen were blood transfusion (21%), followed by uterine incision extension (15%) and atonic PPH (9.4%).

Table 6: Postoperative Complications

Complications	Number	Percentage
Abdominal Distension	34	3.0
Febrile illness	24	2.1
Urine retention	36.8	3.2
Prolong cathetrization	64	5.6
Abdominal woundinfection	23	2.0
Death	0	0

The most common postoperative complications were prolonged catheterization 5.6% followed urine retention 3.2%, and abdominal distension 3.0%.

Discussions

Making a decision of delivery by Cesarean or instrument is difficult. The WHO says that the Robsons classification of CS helps with CS

optimization evaluation of methods intended to reduce the rate of CS.

Jyotsna et al. [3] in their study "foeto-maternal outcome of second stage cesarean section in B.P Koirala institute of health science, a retrospective study" found that the most common indication was arrest of descent and dilatation 40%, and the most common complication was prolonged catheterization 15%.

Dahiya et al. [6] in their study of "Retrospective analysis of second stage of cesarean section and pregnancy outcome, observational study" found that the most common indication was arrest in second stage 56.1% and the most common complication was extension of uterine incision 16.0%, febrile illness 14.1%.

Chandrashekhar AB et al.[1] in their study of "Maternal and fetal outcome in second stage caesarean section: a retrospective study" found that the common intra-operative complications were atonic PPH 25%, hematuria 16.66%, and the postoperative complications were fever 14%, prolonged catheterization 41.6%.

J. Unterscheider et al. [7] in their study "Rising rates of caesarean deliveries at full cervical dilatation: a concerning trend" found that rate of caesarean was 27.5%, 44.1% of women had a second stage caesarean section, 14.3% women had postpartum hemorrhage and 23% women required blood transfusion.

Babre, Vijaya Monish et al. [8] In their study "Review of caesarean sections at full dilatation." found that 11.5% patients had atonic postpartum hemaorrhage, and 3.3% had extension of uterine incision wound. There was increased incidence of postoperative fever.

Gurung Padma et al. [9] in their study "Caesarean Section During Second Stage of Labor in a Tertiary Centre" found that most common indication was cephalopelvic disproportion 92.4%. Most common intraoperative complications were atonic postpartum hemorrhage followed by uterine incision extension 12.5%. Most common postoperative complications were postoperative fever 18.8%, wound infection 4.8%.

Mckelvey A. et al. [10] in their study "Caesarean section in the second stage of labour: A retrospective review of obstetric setting and morbidity" found that most common complications were postpartum hemorrhage, sepsis and uterine tear.

Alexander James. M et al. [11] in their study "Comparison of Maternal and Infant Outcomes From Primary Cesarean Delivery During the Second Compared With First Stage of Labor" found that the maternal composite index was increased due to

uterine atony, uterine incision extension and incidental cystotomy.

Samal R. et al. [12] in their study "Fetomaternal outcome of nulliparous women undergoing caesarean section in first and second stage of labour: A prospective study in a tertiary care centre of Puducherry" found that caesarean in second stage was associated with increased maternal morbidity such as hemorrhage, uterine angle extension, blood transfusion, prolonged hospital stay, febrile morbidity, urinary system injury.

Cebekulu et al [13] in their study "Complications associated with caesarean section in the second stage of labor" found that time taken for surgery was longer in second stage caesarean section and it was associated with more postoperative pyrexia

Trivedi N et al. [2] in their study "Maternal and neonatal outcome in second stage caesarean section" found that 54.55% women belong to the age group 20-25. In present study most women were found to be in 25-30 age group of 43.7%, which may be due to the early age marriage.

In the present study the parity of the patients was found to be 72.2% in primigravida and 27.8% in multigravida which corresponds to the study of Trivedi N et al. [2] 74.55% in primigravida and 25.45% in multigravida.

In the present study the rate of blood transfusion was 21% which was 50.90% in the study done by Trivedi N et al. [2]

In our study the most common indications were arrest of descent 44%, most common intraoperative complications were blood transfusion 21% and the most common postoperative complications were prolonged catheterization 5.6%.

The rate of caesarean section in our study is 48.02% which surpasses the WHO recommended rate of caesarean section of 10-15%. This is because Assam Medical College being tertiary care Centre and all the complicated cases are referred here.

Conclusion

Cesarean section has decreased the maternal mortality and morbidity to much extent. But a vaginal delivery is always preferred. Taking the decision of CS in the second stage is always difficult. A proper evaluation and judgement is required. Although CS in the second stage has reduced the mortalities and morbidities to much extent some morbidities are unavoidable. Hence a proper judgement and a skilled obstetrician must perform to minimize the complications.

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